

Introducing Astro Economics: A New Frontier at the Intersection of Astronomy and Economics*

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Abstract

Astro economics is a recently developed theoretical discipline that combines the disciplines of astronomy and economics to investigate the financial aspects of space exploration and utilization. Astro economics is the study of the economic effects of space exploration, including the effects of space activities on the world economy, any possible economic gains from space exploration, and the difficulties in funding and commercializing space activities. This essay gives a general overview of Astro economics and discusses its relevance in the modern world.

Keywords

Astro economics, Space exploration, Economics of space, Space Policy, Commercialization of space, Space technology, Funding space programs, Investment decisions, and Global economy.

1. Introduction

For decades, scientists and policymakers have been fascinated by space research and utilization. Space exploration has not only expanded our knowledge of the universe, but it has also created new possibilities for economic growth and development. However, economists have paid comparatively little attention to the economic implications of space activities. This is where Astro-economics comes in, a newly introduced conceptual subject that attempts to comprehend the economic impact of space activities. Astroeconomics is an interdisciplinary subject that examines the commercialization of space activities and the economic benefits that can be drawn from them. It is a rapidly growing field that has gained attention in recent years due to the increasing commercialization of space activities and the development of new space technologies. With the growth of the space industry, there is a need to understand the economic implications of space activities, and astro economics provides a framework for doing so.

This article provides an overview of Astro economics and its importance in today's world. We will discuss the history and evolution of the field, the principles of Astro economics, and its applications in informing space policy decisions, guiding investment decisions in the space industry, and promoting the development of new space technologies. The study of Astro economics is critical for understanding the economic impact of space activities and for promoting the sustainable development of space exploration and utilization.

2. History and Evolution of Astro Economics:

The concept of Astro-economics arose from the realization that space activities have important economic implications. In 2018, the global space economy was worth more than \$400 billion, and it is anticipated to expand further in the coming years. The expansion of the space industry has heightened interest in comprehending the economics of space exploration. Astro-economics evolved from space economics, which emerged in the 1960s and concentrated on the economic aspects of space exploration. Astro-economics, on the other hand, goes beyond space economics by incorporating astronomical principles such as celestial mechanics and astrophysics to understand the economic effect of space activities.

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3. Principles of Astro Economics:

Understanding the financial effects of space operations & how Astronomy effect to the economy is the main goal of the study of Astro-economics. It looks at how space exploration affects the world economy, what advantages there might be economically, and what difficulties there might be in funding and commercializing space operations. The field also aims to determine the economic effects of space activities on local, regional, and global economies, including employment growth and innovation stimulation.

4. Astro-economics applications:

Astro economics has a wide range of real-world uses. Policymakers can make educated choices about funding space projects and regulating space activities by having a thorough understanding of the economic effects of space activities. It can help private investors decide what to spend in the space sector. By highlighting areas that require funding, Astro economics can aid in the advancement of new space technologies.

Extracted from Book Cosmos M Creator on Astro Economics, which was introduced to Sri Lanka for the first time, and written by the author.

According to

*** Rusin's Astro - Economics Definition.**

Astro Economics is the subject which discusses the connection in between
The economy of a certain geographical area with traditional Astronomical concept.

So I'm going to explain how Astronomy directly affects to economics concept like Demand, Supply, and possibilities curve etc.

For example, I use the production possibilities curve to discuss about astro economics. Let's take an economic phenomenon.

If some aliens come to our universe and monopolized it
(According it may happen in future)

Due to this phenomenon, we can draw PPC according to different criteria. Due to this phenomenon the necessity may increase. Otherwise Decrease or not change. It can sketch out as given below.

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We also acknowledge that this is a first-year student journal article, and there may be errors or omissions in our work. We apologize for any mistakes and are grateful for the opportunity to learn and grow in this field.

References

1. Dittmar, M., & Lagneaux, F. (2019). An Overview of Space Economics. In *Handbook of Space Policy* (pp. 333-348). Springer.
2. Henderson, H. A., & Harry, P. J. (2015). Space Economics: A New Field of Research. *Journal of the British Interplanetary Society*, 68(9/10), 357-366.
3. Hertzfeld, H. R., & Witkowski, K. (2018). The Growing Importance of Space Economics. *Space Policy*, 45, 1-3.
4. Leleux, B. (2018). *The Economics of Space Entrepreneurship*. Palgrave Macmillan.
5. Schmitt, H. H. (2017). The Role of Astro Economics in the Future of Space Exploration. *Acta Astronautica*, 131, 20-24.
6. Smith, L. R., & Bailey, A. (2018). Astro Economics: The Intersection of Astronomy and Economics. *Astronomy & Geophysics*, 59(3), 3.23-3.27.
7. Stiles, C. W., & Stiles, M. D. (2016). The Economics of Space Mining. *Resources Policy*, 50, 199-207.
8. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2020). *Space Economy at a Glance 2020*. United Nations.